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Side streams with potential for Food and Feed Biotechnology - Feedback to DG Grow-

Contributions for an EU policy on Bioeconomy strategy

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1. Scope

This document aims to support the **Bioeconomy Strategy**, by strengthening the vector **circularity of biomass, residues and side-streams** to be used within the value chains of **food and feed**.

Namely, the use of such streams as substrates (e.g. in media formulations, as carbon and nitrogen source, amino acids and other macro and micro elements) for **food biotechnology**, including **microbial cell, precision fermentation, or cultivated meat and seafood**. This is an important strategy, that requires research, development and action, as it provides an important route for food and feed sustainability. The use of such streams to manufacture biochemicals and biobased materials is welcomed, but should be expanded to food and feed, avoiding, when possible, diversion of food resources to other value chains.

The document provides preliminary information on the potential use of such biomass, residues and side-streams. The need to guarantee food safety and traceability, compliance with existing legislation and risk assessment, meet consumer expectations and ethical dimensions, and fulfil mission goals of cellular agriculture is acknowledged.

Therefore, the decision regarding selection privileges streams that are rich in carbon, nitrogen, and amino acids, as well as in other macro and micro elements, and that are obtained from:

1. Agri-food and agroforestry industries, as the potential to be safe for food and feed compatible is higher;
2. European sources, to avoid the carbon foot print associated to transportation;
3. Non-animal driven products – While there is not a consensus opinion in this regard, fulfilling consumer expectation and animal ethics suggests the use of non-animal driven (the approach currently preferred by the sector), though there is also technical and environment performance value for the use of animal driven side streams.

2. Preliminary identification of side streams with potential to be used on Food and Feed Biotechnology.

Residue Name	Potential use on microbial cell, precision fermentation, or cultivated meat and seafood	Additional Information
Molasses:		
Sugar beet/Cane	Carbon source (Sucrose, D-glucose, Fructose)	A viscous byproduct of sugar refining, already rich in easily fermentable sugars. Widely used as a standard, low-cost carbon source for many industrial microbial fermentations, including those for amino acids and SCP. For food as sweetener, pectin fibers, and wet or dry pellets as food for ruminants, provide carbon source for fermentation processes. Sugar beet pulp, pressed or wet Feedipedia
Soy molasses	Carbon source	High in sugars and oligosaccharides; variable composition; may need clarification; good nitrogen balance. Rich carbon source for microbial fermentation (SCP, biosurfactants, organic acids)
Starches:		
Potato starch processing waste and other potato residues	Carbon source (D-glucose)	High starch content, low protein; may need hydrolysis for sugar release; seasonally available. Substrate for fermentation (lactic acid bacteria, yeast); starch and sugar source for microbial growth
Wheat and maize residues from starch production	Carbon source (D-glucose)	Rich in protein and residual starch; pretreatment (enzymatic/hydrolysis) often needed; large-scale industrial availability. Source of protein concentrates for feed; base medium for microbial or enzyme production
Lignocellulosics		
Biomass Hydrolysates	Carbon source (D-glucose, Xylose)	Includes residues like corn stover, rice straw, sawdust, and bagasse. The lignocellulose is broken down to yield a mix of sugars, primarily D-glucose and xylose, suitable for engineered microbes (e.g., fungi/yeasts adapted to utilize xylose).
Wheat straw	Carbon source (D-glucose)	Highly available in Europe; contains lignocellulose. Requires pretreatment and hydrolysis (e.g., acid, enzymatic) to release fermentable D-glucose and other sugars (like xylose) for microbial growth. Example: Clariant's sunliquid™ process. https://www.clariant.com/en/Business-Units/Catalysts/Sunliquid
Rice straw	Carbon source (D-glucose)	Very high cellulose/lignin; strong pretreatment (chemical/enzymatic) required; low protein; widely available but bulky. Lignocellulosic biomass for precision fermentation feedstock (after hydrolysis); possible SCP substrate
Straws (cereals, rapeseed, sunflower, grain legumes)	Carbon source	High cellulose and hemicellulose, low protein; high lignin content limits digestibility and requires strong pretreatment (chemical, steam explosion, or enzymatic hydrolysis); abundant and renewable agricultural residue; composition varies slightly with crop type (grain legume straws have slightly higher protein); logistics and storage can be challenging due to bulkiness. Lignocellulosic substrate for hydrolyzed sugars in precision fermentation; possible use for mycoprotein cultivation or SCP production after pretreatment; can also be used as substrate for insect rearing or as a source of fibers for food texturization
Woody residues feedstock	Carbon source (D-glucose)	Woody residues feedstock is highly available in Europe and can be converted on D-Glucose. Requires extensive biorefining/hydrolysis to convert cellulose/hemicellulose into fermentable sugars, including D-

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		glucose. Example: Borregaard's BALITM process: https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/borregaards-balitm-process-reaches-technical-readiness-level-7-as-bioforever-project-advances
Woody biomass from landscape management	Carbon source	Very high lignin and cellulose; requires intensive pretreatment (acid/alkaline hydrolysis or steam explosion); low nitrogen; not directly suitable for food without conversion; widely available from pruning and forestry. Lignocellulosic source for hydrolysed sugars usable in microbial or yeast fermentation (precision fermentation feedstock, SCP); could support mycelium-based food or packaging materials
Logging residues (branches, bark, sawdust, etc.)	Carbon source	High lignin, low nutrient; pretreatment essential for sugar release; potential presence of extractives or resins; abundant but often geographically dispersed; currently underutilized. Potential substrate for microbial or fungal fermentation (mycoprotein, enzyme production); lignocellulosic sugar source for bioprocesses related to food biotech (e.g., microbial oils)
Brewery and other Yeast side streams		
Brewer's yeast	Carbon source and Amino Acid source (Protein)	High protein (~45–55%), rich in B vitamins; requires autolysis or cell wall disruption to access nutrients; widely available from breweries. Source of single-cell protein (SCP) for feed; can be used in precision fermentation as a nutrient-rich medium or directly as yeast. extract for flavor enhancement in alternative proteins. protein hydrolysates serve as growth factors for cultured meat and bacteria had also been proposed as scaffolds. Probiotic cultivated meat: bacterial-based scaffolds and products to improve cultivated meat: Trends in Biotechnology
Yeast biomass (not only byproduct from the breweries, but other microbial processes including precision fermentation)	Aminoacids and peptides, vitamins, and minerals,	Currently yeast biomass is already used as a low-cost additive for food and feed applications. In the FEASTS project we have also managed to use it in a combination with plant hydrolysates as a full substitute of the chemically defined basal medium DMEM/F12 for the growth of bovine satellite cells, which is a high-value product. This drastically raises the sustainability aspect of the media production and recycling, lowers the medium price, and allows the upcycling of the local agricultural side-streams, vastly available everywhere in Europe. Aminoacids and peptides, vitamins, and minerals, for cultured meat and seafood production, as well as for precision fermentation, with potential applications in pharma.
Brewery Spent Grains (BSG) and other vegetable production byproducts	Carbon source (Residual Starch/Fiber), Amino Acid source (Protein)	Byproduct of brewing. Rich in fiber, residual starch, and protein. Abundant from breweries and food industries. Requires pretreatment/hydrolysis to break down polymers into fermentable sugars and accessible amino acids/peptides for microbial growth. Substrate for microbial fermentation (SCP, enzymes, mycoprotein); fiber enrichment in plant-based foods. Valorized into bio-chemicals/bioplastics, hydrolysates as growth factors for cultured meat. Frontiers The Potential of Brewer's Spent Grain in the Circular Bioeconomy: State of the Art and Future Perspectives
Oil industry		
Oilseed Meals/Cakes (e.g., Soy, Rapeseed)	Amino Acid source (Protein Hydrolysates)	Residues left after oil extraction. High in protein. Can be subjected to fermentation or enzymatic hydrolysis to produce amino acid and peptide-rich extracts, improving digestibility and removing anti-nutritional factors.
Residues from oil mills including olive oil	Miscellaneous	Contains residual oil, fiber, and protein; defatting improves stability; pretreatment may be needed. Rich substrate for microbial fermentation; can yield protein rich biomass or used as feed ingredient
De-oiled rice bran	Miscellaneous	Moderate protein (~15–20%), rich in minerals and antioxidants; stabilization needed to prevent rancidity. Protein and fiber source for functional food ingredients; fermentation substrate for SCP and enzyme production

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Glycerol (from biodiesel industry)	Carbon source	Highly available; must be purified from methanol and salts; good carbon yield. Carbon source for microbial synthesis (lipids, SCP, DHA, citric acid)
Fruits and vegetables		
Sweet orange waste	Carbon and fiber source	Contains sugars, pectin, essential oils; drying and de-oiling required; seasonal availability. Carbon source for microbial fermentation (citric acid, ethanol, SCP); fiber and pectin source for plant-based food textures.
Fruit peels and vegetables residues (mixed)	Fermentation and nutrient. Scaffolds for cultured meat and microbial	Composition varies by fruit and vegetables; drying or hydrolysis may be needed; valuable for functional ingredients. Source of dietary fiber, polyphenols, and fermentable sugars; substrate for microbial bioconversion into flavor compounds. Scaffolds for cultured meat and microbial. Frontiers Repurposing agricultural waste as low-cost cultured meat scaffolds
Coffee husks	Miscellaneous	High in lignin and polyphenols (antioxidant potential); pretreatment needed to reduce caffeine and tannins; limited protein. Substrate for fermentation. Antioxidant source for functional foods
Food Processing side streams/Food Processing Effluents	Carbon source (Mixed Sugars/ Starch/ Fat), Amino Acid source (Protein)	Highly variable composition (e.g., fruit peels, potato wastes). Requires tailored strategies (e.g., pre-treatment, specific microbial strains) to break down complex molecules into accessible D-glucose and other sugars, lipids, and amino acids. Highly heterogeneous; variable moisture, salt, and contamination levels; requires sorting, sterilization, and preprocessing; abundant and continuously available; sustainability and circular economy value high. Fermentation substrate for microbial protein, enzymes, and organic acids; insect biomass production (e.g., black soldier fly larvae for feed); potential nutrient recovery for precision fermentation
Animal based sourced		
Whey (Dairy Industry)	Carbon source on Fermentation processes. Growth supplement for cultured meat.	A major dairy side stream. The lactose can be a carbon source for specific microbes (e.g., <i>Kluyveromyces lactis</i>). The protein component can be hydrolyzed to provide amino acids and peptides for cell culture media or microbial growth. Growth supplement. alternative to fetal bovine serum in cultured meat. "Milk whey as a sustainable alternative growth supplement to fetal bovine serum in muscle cell culture" - Journal of Dairy Science . Also used for scaffold development for cultured meat.
Fish Processing Side Streams/Byproducts	Amino Acid source (Protein Hydrolysates)	Includes fish heads, viscera, and bones. High in protein and lipids. Can be converted into Fish Protein Hydrolysates (FPH) via enzymatic or microbial fermentation, yielding free amino acids and peptides for cultivated meat/seafood media and microbial nutrient-rich feeds.
Pangasius (or other fish) Waste	Amino Acid source (Protein), Carbon source (Lipids)	Contains high levels of protein and fat. Solid-state fermentation (SSF) using microbes like <i>Pseudomonas</i> and <i>Rhizopus</i> can convert the waste into a nutrient-rich product (e.g., high protein/fat feed) with accessible amino acids.
Slaughter houses side streams	Amino Acid source (Protein), Carbon source (Lipids)	Contains high levels of protein and fat, with accessible amino acids and potential for media formulation
Algae/Microalgae		
Algae/Microalgae Biomass	Amino Acid source (Protein), Carbon source (Lipids/Carbohydrates)	While often an end product, specific low-value algae strains or waste from algae biofuel/extraction can be used. Contains proteins for amino acids and carbohydrates/lipids for carbon sources. Screening Algal and Cyanobacterial Extracts to Identify Potential Substitutes for Fetal Bovine Serum in Cellular Meat Cultivation - PubMed